

Comparative studies of Pb^{II} remediation by zero-valent iron and bimetallic Ni/Fe nanoparticles

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Abstract : In this study synthesized bimetallic Ni/Fe nanoparticles (Ni/Fe NPs) and zero-valent iron NPs (nZVI) were investigated for remediation of Pb^{II} against the effect of various process parameters on removal efficiency. Results of the present study suggested both Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs and nZVI have shown maximum removal of Pb^{II} at pH 5 which enhanced with increasing pH. The *v/m* ratio study showed that the same volume of lead solution required more bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs than nZVI with identical equilibrium time whereas less corrosion of Ni/Fe NPs showed higher removal efficiency than nZVI at more acidic pH. The values of separation factor were between zero and one indicating favourable sorption for Pb^{II} on both the tested sorbents. Sorption equilibrium isotherms were plotted for metal uptake capacity (*q*) against different variables studied. Results on adsorption isotherms suggested that adsorption process on Ni/Fe NPs followed Freundlich model i.e. heterogeneous in nature whereas that on nZVI obeyed both Langmuir model i.e. homogeneous and Freundlich model. Catalytic action of nickel counterpart of Ni/Fe NPs and subsequent reversible oxidation and reduction of Ni⁰ on its surfaces make more efficient sorbents than nZVI.

Keywords : Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs, catalytic reduction, adsorption isotherm, Pb^{II} remediation, Langmuir and Freundlich model.

Introduction

Lead poisoning may be acute or chronic, but the latter is much more common¹. Authorities such as the American Academy of Pediatrics define lead poisoning as blood lead levels higher than 10 µg/L². The U.S. EPA action level for Pb is 0.015 mg/L. Additionally the EPA has set a Maximum Contaminant Level Goal for Pb of 0 mg/L³. It is therefore, important to monitor the lead level seriously in the environmental samples.

Literature resources have reported redox mechanisms for a number of cations by nZVI e.g. Pb^{II} and Cr^{VI}³, As^{III} and As^V^{4,5}, Cu^{II}⁶, Ag^I⁷ and Co^{II}⁸. Several recent studies provided valuable insights into key nZVI properties associated with the potential to transform metal ions

such as Cd, Ni, Zn, As, Cr, Cu, Ag and Pb, as well as notorious inorganic anions like perchlorate and nitrate^{3,9-10}. Laboratory research has established that nanoscale metallic iron is very effective in destroying a wide variety of common contaminants^{3,4,9-14}. Recent report has suggested that supported and unsupported nano-iron were clearly superior to iron filings in short-term batch remediation reactions of aqueous Cr^{VI}, Pb^{II} and TcO₄¹².

Nickel-iron NPs (NPs) (1 : 3 Ni : Fe) with high surface area to volume ratio showed 50–80 times higher degradation rate for the dehalogenation of trichloroethylene (TCE) compared to nanoiron or iron filings¹⁵. With bimetallic particles, it has been demonstrated that Fe or

Zn acts as the reductant for water and the second metal, Pd, Pt, Ag, or Ni, acts as a catalyst¹⁶. Also, Ni-Fe nanoparticle-laden films were observed to exhibit better tribiological properties than those containing the mono-metallic species which suggested that combination of NPs could be used to derive greater benefits¹⁷ with improved catalytic activity as well as new properties¹⁸.

The bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs were more effective towards degradation of dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT)¹⁹ and Orange G²⁰ than nZVI. The continuous efforts to improve the performance of the zero-valent metal technology led to the use of bimetallic NPs such as Pd/Fe, Pd/Mg, Ni/Fe^{16,21}. The introduction of catalytic metal Pd could increase surface area. However, high cost of Pd noble metal limits its wide application for pollutant treatment. Instead of Pd, Ni could be used as the catalyst as it is cheap.

The objectives of the present study were to (i) prepare nZVI and bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs, (ii) characterize them by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), EDX (Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy), XRD (Powder X-ray diffraction), TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy), XPS (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) and FAAS (Flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy), (iii) apply them to remove Pb^{II} in aqueous solution optimizing process parameters such as pH, v/m ratio, contact time, and initial concentration of Pb^{II} and Pb^{IV} to compare the removal efficiency between nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs.

Results and discussion

The rate of degradation of DDT and TCE by Ni/Fe was about 50–80 times greater than the degradation rate of DDT and TCE by nZVI^{15,22,23}, the present study took initiative to check whether Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs can remove Pb^{II} from aqueous solution similarly or not, since the addition of Ni could limit the nanocrystalline growth of Fe and decrease the particle size of Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs¹⁹. Although there are few literature on nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs during last two years, so far our knowledge concerned no direct study on removal of Pb^{II} using nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs are found^{24–29}.

Characterization of NPs :

Fig. 1 shows the XRD spectrum of nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs. The characteristic basic reflection peak at 44.70° indicates mainly the formation of nanoiron in zero valent state (Fig. 1a) whereas no sharp peak (zig zag/wave in

Fig. 1. Powder XRD pattern for (a) nZVI and (b) bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs.

nature) for bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs indicates its amorphous nature (Fig. 1b). Other published literatures also suggested the same amorphous nature for bimetallic NPs^{19,30–32}. Literature resources indicate that nZVI possess a core-shell structure, in which the shell represents the oxidized part that surrounds the Fe⁰ core and preserves it against further oxidation^{4,5,10,12,33,34}. In the case of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs, Ni takes part of oxygen forming amorphous shell of 3–5 nm thick and prevents oxidation of Fe⁰ core as well as agglomeration³⁴.

Schrack *et al.*¹⁵ calculated surface area of 59 m² g⁻¹ with a chemical composition of 53.1% Fe and 15.6% Ni of non-spherical bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs. In the present study the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis showed the surface area of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs as 73.6 m² g⁻¹ with a composition of 73.84% of iron and 26.16% of nickel which may imply greater surface activities towards adsorption than nZVI (having surface area of 36 m² g⁻¹).

EDX spectrum shows the chemical/elemental analysis of nZVI (Fig. 2a) and bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 2b). Result of EDX study shows that bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs consisted of 73.84% of iron, 26.16% of nickel (weight %) and 74.79% of iron, 25.21% of nickel (atomic %) whereas nZVI consisted of 90.26% of Fe, 9.74% of O (weight %) and 72.65% of Fe, 27.35% of O (atomic %).

orientation of materials making up the sample. It was clear from the two dimensional SEM images of nZVI and bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 3a, 3c) that both were spherical in shape and the size of the particles was below 100 nm which is supported by particle size analysis and manual calculation of particle size distribution of nZVI using Fig. 3a (supporting document S1b and S3). Similar infor-

Fig. 2. EDX spectrum for (a) nZVI and (b) bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs.

Tee and co-workers²³ used bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs for dechlorination and found that a maximum rate of dechlorination was achieved with a Ni content of 25 wt%, similar to the Ni/Fe ratio designed by Schrick *et al.*¹⁵ to get the faster TCE dechlorination rate. In the present study the synthesized bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs were mostly similar to them^{15,22}. In addition, the increase in Ni content beyond this level was attributed to high levels of Ni with respect to Fe at the particle edges, which hindered the ability of Fe to transfer electrons to the reaction sites and hence decreased in efficiency of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs^{15,22}.

SEM analysis was used to get external morphology (texture), chemical composition, crystalline structure and

information was obtained from TEM analysis (Fig. 3b, 3d). Particle size analysis and manual calculation of particle size distribution of Ni/Fe NPs using Fig. 3b (supporting document S1a and S2) support the above findings on sizes of Ni/Fe NPs. Nurmi *et al.*³⁵ found that nZVI powders (having < 1.5 nm crystals) were aggregated into approximately spherical 20 to 100 nm diameter particles, which were ultimately aggregated into the chains and further linked into clusters of chains (Fig. 3b)³⁵. Other reports^{3,13} also reported similar chain-like aggregates of nZVI. However, in the present study it was evident that introduction of Ni reduced or stopped the chain-like aggregates of nZVI and formed spherical core-shell typed

Fig. S1. Particle size distribution of (a) ZVI NPs (using Fig. 3b) and (b) Ni/Fe NPs (using Fig. 3d) by manual counting.

NPs with complete dispersion. X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) study showed the surface composition of nZVI (Fig. 4a), Fe in bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 4b) and Ni in bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 4c).

Remediation of Pb^{II} by bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs :

The nZVI [Fe^{II}/Fe] has a standard reduction potential (E^0) of -0.44 V, which is lower than that of many metals such as Pb, Cd, Ni, and Cr, as well as many organic compounds like chlorinated hydrocarbons. These compounds are thus susceptible to the reduction by nZVI³⁵ and could be useful for the separation and transformation of a variety of contaminants¹⁰. Although nZVI used to remove Pb^{II} from solutions^{11,12} there was no report on the usage of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs as adsorbent for the removal of Pb^{II} from liquid samples. Since the removal efficiency depends upon various parameters such as pH, time of contact, v/m ratio and initial concentration of the metal ion, the effect of these parameters on the removal efficiency was monitored in the present study after optimizing each.

The study of pH effect on removal efficiency of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 5a) showed that removal efficiency

Fig. S2. Particle size analysis of Ni/Fe NPs.

Fig. S3. Particle size analysis of ZVI NPs.

Fig. 3. SEM images for (a) nZVI and (c) bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs and TEM images for (b) nZVI and (d) bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs.

Fig. 4. XPS spectrum for (a) nZVI, (b) Fe in bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs and (c) Ni in bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs.

increased with increasing pH (95.8% to 99.1%). The maximum removal (99.1%) took place at pH 5. Therefore, pH was optimized at pH 5 for removal study using bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs. Normally solution pH affects the surface charge of adsorption and the degree of ionization with speciation of adsorbate during reaction. Because the disappearance of nZVI by iron corrosion could be accelerated in acidic condition i.e. at the lower pH and hence

reactivity decreased at the lower pH in the present study. A thorough investigation on change in solution pH immediately after addition of sorbent and after completion of stirring shows that after addition of sorbent to Pb^{II} solution pH changed to 5.3 ~ 5.4 from pH 5.0 and pH changed to ~ 7.0 after 24 h of stirring (data not shown). In case of nZVI the corrosion product surfaces are negative [$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-O}^-$] which causes electrostatic repulsion at basic conditions⁴. Therefore, adsorption preferably occurs on nZVI surfaces between pH 4 and pH 9. As long as there is an electronic bridge between the two metals in Ni/Fe NPs and the presence of metallic iron, Pb^{II} adsorption at the sorbent surface will continue³⁶.

The removal efficiency decreased with increase in the v/m ratio (Fig. 5b). More than 99% removal of Pb^{II} took place in the v/m ratio of 300 compared to 100% removal of Pb^{II} for the v/m ratios of 100 and 200. Therefore, v/m ratio was optimized as 200 i.e. 0.05 g of adsorbent for 20 ml of 50 mg L^{-1} Pb^{II} solution was fixed to study the effects of contact time and initial load of Pb^{II} using Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs in the present study. Kinetic experiments showed that the removal efficiency increased with contact time (Fig. 5c). Almost 100% removal of Pb^{II} took place at a contact time of 4 h. Therefore, the contact time was optimized as 4 h in the present study.

The variation in the uptake capacity of Ni/Fe NPs with initial concentration of Pb^{II} solutions showed that the removal efficiency decreased from 99.1% to 96.3% with increase in the initial concentrations of Pb^{II} solution from 500 mg L^{-1} to 3000 mg L^{-1} (Fig. 5d). In all cases (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5c, 5d) metal uptake capacity (q) was plotted against study variable. The results (Fig. 5d) show that Pb^{II} uptake capacity (mg g^{-1}) is proportional at all initial concentrations studied.

Remediation of Pb^{II} by nZVI :

Similarly, removal efficiency of nZVI was checked under different conditions. It was found that the removal efficiency increased with pH of the test solution (Fig. 6a). The maximum removal took place at pH 5. Therefore, the pH was optimized at pH 5 for other studies using nZVI. The effect of pH on removal of Pb^{II} from solution was more on nZVI than bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs, because nZVI removed 95.6% compared to 99% by Ni/Fe NPs. The higher corrosion of nZVI over Ni/Fe bime-

Fig. 5. Removal efficiency (%) and Pb^{II} uptake capacity (mg g⁻¹) of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs – (a) effect of pH, (b) effect of *v/m* ratio, (c) effect of contact time (h) and (d) effect of initial load of Pb^{II} (mg L⁻¹). The experimental conditions are same as mentioned in the text.

tallic NPs caused this discrepancy. Presumably, the corrosion of iron was the rate limited reaction under the experimental condition of the present study.

The removal efficiency decreased with increase in *v/m* ratio (Fig. 6b). Complete removal of Pb^{II} took place in the *v/m* ratio of 400. Therefore, *v/m* ratio was optimized at 400 throughout the present study. This result shows that nZVI were more effective to remove Pb^{II} from the solution, because maximum removal was obtained at a *v/m* ratio of 400 for nZVI compared to a *v/m* ratio of 200 for Ni/Fe NPs. Also, the removal efficiency increased with contact time (Fig. 6c). Almost 100% removal of Pb^{II} took place at a contact time of 4 h. Therefore, the contact time was optimized as 4 h of duration for the study of other parameters. In both the cases equilibrium was attained at a contact time of 4 h (Fig. 5c and Fig. 6c). In addition, the removal efficiency of nZVI decreased with increase in the initial concentrations of Pb^{II} solution from 500 mg L⁻¹ to 4000 mg L⁻¹ (Fig. 6d). At the highest studied initial concentration (i.e. 3000 mg L⁻¹), the amount of Pb^{II} on Ni/Fe NPs was 2311 mg Pb^{II} g⁻¹ Ni/Fe NPs (Fig. 5d) and it further confirmed more absorp-

tion capacity of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs over nZVI (2275 mg Pb^{II} g⁻¹ nZVI) (Fig. 5d vs Fig. 6d). Although the rate of DDT degradation using bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs was greater than that of nZVI^{9,10,19,23,30}, probably the presence of Ni in Ni/Fe NPs promoted the degradation reaction of DDT, TCE and PCP via catalytic activity¹⁹ which was observed similarly in the present study. Further, the flow of electrons from Fe-surface to the outer surface was prohibited to a significant extent by the Ni-shell surrounding nZVI cores (Fig. 3d) which increases the stability of Ni/Fe NPs. In all cases (Fig. 6a, 6b, 6c, 6d) metal uptake capacity (*q*) was plotted against study variable. The results (Fig. 6d) show that Pb^{II} uptake capacity (mg g⁻¹) is proportional at all initial concentrations studied.

Table 1 shows comparative uptake values of Pb^{II} by nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs. The results show that nZVI particles were better adsorbent than Ni/Fe NPs towards adsorption of Pb^{II} since *v/m* ratio and initial load for nZVI were just twice these values for Ni/Fe NPs (Table 1). Although surface areas of Ni/Fe NPs are higher than surface areas of nZVI (73.6 m² g⁻¹ vs 36 m² g⁻¹) the adsorption capacity of Ni/Fe NPs (31.4 mg Pb^{II} m⁻²) was lower than nZVI (63.2 mg Pb^{II} m⁻²) considering initial

Fig. 6. Removal efficiency (%) and uptake capacity (mg g^{-1}) of nZVI – (a) effect of pH, (b) effect of v/m ratio, (c) effect of contact time (h) and (d) effect of initial load of lead (mg L^{-1}). The experimental conditions are same as mentioned in the text.

concentration of 3000 mg L^{-1} for each sorbent, because Ni in the outer shell of Ni/Fe NPs prohibited the flow of electrons from inner core Fe^0 nanoparticles to the surface and hence reduced the rate of reduction of Pb^{II} and subsequent adsorption which was highly supported by our experimental findings (Table 1).

Adsorption isotherms :

Table 1. Comparison of uptake values of Pb^{II} by nZVI and Ni/Fe nanoparticles

Optimized parameters	Maximum uptake of Pb^{II} (in %) by Ni/Fe NPs	Maximum uptake of Pb^{II} (in %) by nZVI
pH	5 (99.1)	5 (71.3)
Contact time (h)	4 (99.4)	4 (99.8)
Initial load (mg L^{-1})	500 (99.1)	1000 (100)
v/m ratio (mL g^{-1})	200 (100)	400 (100)

Langmuir isotherm³⁷ which assumes homogeneous distribution of binding sites over the surface of the adsorbent and Freundlich isotherm³⁸ which assumed surface of adsorbent to be heterogeneous towards adsorbates were checked in the present study. The Langmuir model assumes the formation of monolayer adsorption at constant adsorption energy while the Freundlich model deals with

heterogeneous adsorption. Langmuir equation of adsorption isotherm is $1/q = 1/q_{\text{max}} + 1/(b \cdot q_{\text{max}})(C_f)$, where q_{max} and b are the Langmuir constants. The plot of $1/q$ vs $1/C_f$ is linear and q_{max} is determined from slope of the line whereas b is calculated from intercept. Constant b which is related to the energy of adsorption through the Arrhenius equation estimates the affinity of the sorbent to the metal ions. q_{max} predicts the total number of binding sites that are available for sorption and q quantifies the number of binding sites that are occupied already by the metal ions at the concentration of C_f ³⁹.

Adsorption-partition constants are determined for metal using the Freundlich equation of adsorption isotherm as $\log q = \log K + (1/n) \log C_f$, where q is the metal ion sorbed (mg g^{-1}), C_f is the equilibrium concentration of metal ion solution in mg L^{-1} , K and n are Freundlich constants. K is a measure of the degree or strength of adsorption and the value of K is proportional to adsorption while $1/n$ is used as an indication of isocratic adsorption (at $1/n = 1$) or decreases with increasing metal ions concentrations (with $1/n \neq 1$)⁴⁰. The constants K and $1/n$ were determined from slopes and intercepts of the plot between $\log q$ and $\log C_f$.

The results of regression coefficients (R^2 and K) for bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs suggest that adsorption of Pb^{II} onto adsorbent surface was mostly heterogeneous in nature ($R^2 = 0.92$ and $K = 308 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$) instead of homogeneous surfaces ($R^2 = 0.72$ and $K = 280 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 7a and 7b). The results of regression coefficients (R^2) (0.96 vs 0.83) from similar type of plots for nZVI suggest that adsorption of Pb^{II} onto nZVI fitted both the models reasonably well in the present study (Fig. 7c and 7d). The results of q_{max} also prefer Langmuir adsorption isotherm for nZVI over Ni/Fe NPs towards adsorption of Pb^{II} from its aqueous solution in equilibrium (Table 1).

In the present study SP is plotted against initial concentration of Pb^{II} solution (Fig. 8) and it shows that sorption isotherm is favourable at all initial concentration investigated. Fig. 8a shows that the values of SP is between zero and one indicating favourable sorption even at the highest initial concentration of 3000 mg L^{-1} Pb^{II} onto Ni/Fe NPs and Fig. 8b shows that the values of SP is between zero and one indicating favourable sorption even at the highest initial concentration of 4000 mg L^{-1} Pb^{II} onto nZVI.

Isotherm constants of Langmuir and Freundlich models for Pb^{II} absorption onto nZVI and bimetallic Ni/Fe

Fig. 7. Adsorption isotherm for Pb^{II} adsorption onto bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs and nZVI - (a) Langmuir isotherm for Ni/Fe NPs, (b) Freundlich isotherm for Ni/Fe NPs, (c) Langmuir isotherm for nZVI and (d) Freundlich isotherm for nZVI.

The shape of the Langmuir isotherm can be used to predict whether a sorption model is favourable or unfavourable in a batch adsorption process from dimensionless equilibrium parameter or separation factor (SF). It is determined as $SF = 1/(1 + bC_i)$, where b , the constant from Langmuir equation and C_i , the initial metal ion concentration (mg L^{-1}). The parameter, SF, indicates the shape of the isotherm and nature of the sorption process. SP values between 0 and 1 indicate favourable adsorption, while $SP > 1$, $SP = 1$, and $SP = 0$ indicate unfavourable, linear, and irreversible adsorption isotherms^{40,41}.

NPs are summarized in Table 2. The results imply that the value of q_{max} (mg g^{-1}) for nZVI was 12.7 fold lower than that of Ni/Fe NPs whereas R^2 value was higher (0.83 vs 0.72). Hence isotherm constants favoured Langmuir model for absorption of Pb^{II} by nZVI. In addition the value of n for Ni/Fe NPs was 5.24 which is slightly higher than that of nZVI ($n = 4.57$) indicating Freundlich model for Ni/Fe NPs towards absorption of Pb^{II} from its aqueous solution (Table 2). These results clearly agree to the theoretical expectation of homogeneous and heterogeneous models in adsorption study using nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs sorbents.

Fig. 8. A plot of SF against initial concentration of lead (mg L⁻¹) for (a) Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs and (b) nZVI.

Table 2. Isotherm constants of Langmuir and Freundlich models for Pb^{II} absorption onto nZVI and bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs

	Parameters	nZVI	Ni/Fe NPs
Langmuir	q_{max} (mg g ⁻¹)	0.39	4.95
	b	5.02	4.7
	R^2	0.83	0.72
Freundlich	K (L mg ⁻¹)	280	308
	N	4.57	5.24
	R^2	0.96	0.92

Plausible mechanism :

On the basis of all our results on adsorption study the plausible mechanisms for removal of Pb^{II} by both nZVI and Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs are explained schematically in Fig. 9. At equilibrium time less corrosion of Ni/Fe NPs showed higher removal efficiency than nZVI at lower pH (Fig. 5a and Fig. 6a). This observation implies that corrosion of the iron surface in nZVI would lead to the formation of a surface-passivating iron oxide layer at lower pH i.e. at more acidic solution and this surface passivation dominates the overall reduction process and hinders the removal of Pb^{II} onto the iron surface. On the other hand, the presence of Ni (which has lower hydrogen overpotential than Fe) in Ni/Fe bimetallic NP system prevents the development of an oxide film by forming a Fe-

Fig. 9. A model for core-shell structure of Ni/Fe NPs and uptake mechanisms of Pb^{II} ions. (1) Adsorption of Pb²⁺, (2) Oxidation of shell Ni⁰ to Ni²⁺, (3) Reduction of Pb²⁺ to Pb⁰, (4) Oxidation of core Fe⁰ to Fe²⁺, (5) Reduction of Ni²⁺ to Ni⁰.

Ni redox couple on the nanoparticle surface until nickel remains in the zero-valent state and increases catalytic reduction of Pb^{II} ions after sorption onto Ni-surface^{15,19,20,6}. Ultimately, this process increases adsorptive removal of Pb^{II} by Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs compared to nZVI.

Although the removal of Pb^{II} via adsorption process predominantly occurs via a catalytic reductive pathway and subsequently would lead to oxidative mechanism as the reaction progresses with time which leads to reusability of Ni/Fe NPs.

Basically, electrons from oxidation of the Fe⁰ core are transported through the iron oxide/catalytic Ni-shell to reduce adsorbed Pb^{II} ions to Pb⁰. Pb has substantial initial deposition overpotential and therefore tends to grow in dendritic fashion. The high surface area of these deposits may favor adsorption of Pb^{II}³.

The mechanisms can vary with the standard electrode potential of the sorbate ion, its charge density, and the operating experimental conditions, in particular pH of the medium in comparison with the iso-electric point (IEP) of nZVI surface. If (i) the standard reduction potential (E^0) of cation is more negative than or close to that of Fe, physical sorption of cation takes place onto the surface of NPs; (ii) if standard reduction potential of cation is slightly more positive than that of Fe, both sorption and chemical reduction arises for cations; and (iii) if standard reduction potential of cation is substantially higher than that of Fe, only chemical reduction occurs⁴².

In the case of Pb^{II} ions (with E^0 of -0.35 V) both

sorption and chemical reduction took place simultaneously on the surfaces of Ni/Fe NPs [eqs. (1–4)]⁴². The reduction process [eq. (2)] was accelerated catalytically by the shell of core-shell Ni/Fe NPs.

Experimental

Reagents : Ferrous sulphate (FeSO₄·7H₂O), nickel nitrate [Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O], absolute ethanol, lead nitrate [Pb(NO₃)₂] and sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) were analytical grade and collected from Sd-fine chemicals. A 1000 mg L⁻¹ of Pb²⁺ stock solutions was prepared and used throughout the study. Milli-Q water was used throughout the experiments.

Instruments : A Medium duty stirrer with PMDC motor, stirring shaft and propeller in SS 316 with digital speed indicator and speed regulator, Technico glove box, Powder XRD (Bruker D8 Advance), SEM-EDS (Carl Zeiss, EVO MA 15, Oxford Instruments Inca Penta FET x3), TEM (Philips Tecnai-12, FEI, Netherlands), XPS (Thermo Fisher Scientific Multilab 2000, England), FAAS (AA240, Varian, Australia), and Roto Spin were used for synthesis as well as characterization of NPs.

Characterization of NPs : The morphology and size of solid nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs were characterized using powder XRD, SEM/EDX, TEM and XPS prior to adsorption experiments. Powder XRD analysis was carried out with CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). XRD pattern of nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs were recorded over a 2 θ range of 10–90°. SEM/EDX analysis was carried out after solid samples were sprinkled on the adhesive metallic disk supported carbon tape. Simultaneously, EDX spectrum was recorded at selected areas on the solid surface to obtain the information on surface atomic distribution. Particle sizes of nZVI and Ni/Fe NPs were determined using TEM operating at an accelerated voltage of 100 kV and a resolution of 2 \AA . Elemental speciation analysis was done by XPS instrument with AlK α radiation of 1486.8 eV. The surface area of nanoparticles were measured by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) N₂ method (ASAP 2020, Micromeritics, USA).

Analytical procedures :

Synthesis of nZVI : Zero-valent iron NPs were synthesized by sodium borohydride reduction method which is discussed in details elsewhere^{12,43,44}. Zero-valent iron NPs were synthesized by sodium borohydride reduction method. In brief, 2.4 g FeSO₄·7H₂O was dissolved in 350 ml of ultra pure water. Also, 0.2 g of NaBH₄ was dissolved in 50 ml of water separately and was added dropwise to the above solution with constant stirring. Black particles of zero valent iron NPs were appeared immediately after introducing the first drop of NaBH₄ solution. After the addition of NaBH₄ solution, the mixture was stirred for about 20 min at 500 rpm. Zero-valent iron NPs formed were collected and centrifuged, washed three times with absolute ethanol. After washing the particles were filtered, dried and pulverized.

Synthesis of Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs : The bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs were synthesized by modifying the method described by Tian *et al.*¹⁹. In brief, Ni/Fe NPs were synthesized by borohydride reduction method. 2.4 g FeSO₄·7H₂O and 0.72 g Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Ni/Fe molar ratio of 1 : 3.5) were dissolved in 350 ml of Milli-Q water, which had been deoxygenated by purging N₂ for 20 min. Then, 0.2 g of NaBH₄ was dissolved in 50 ml of water and this was added dropwise to the above solution. Black particles of Ni/Fe NPs were appeared immediately after introducing the first drop of NaBH₄ solution. After the addition of the NaBH₄ solution, the mixture was stirred for about 20 min at 500 rpm. The Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs formed were collected, centrifuged and washed three times with absolute ethanol. After washing the particles were filtered, dried and pulverized. The colour of Ni/Fe bimetallic nanoparticle synthesized was not changed during storage at room temperature.

Remediation of Pb^{II} by nZVI and Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs : A 20 ml of Pb^{II} stock solutions (i.e. 20 mg Pb^{II} per reagent bottle) was pipetted out into each of the reagent bottles and the pH of the solutions was adjusted to 2, 3, 4 and 5 using 0.1 N HCl solution. The pH could not be maintained above 5 as the lead precipitated at higher pH. A 0.05 g of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs was added to each of these reagent bottles and was shaken for 24 h at 50 rpm inside a glove box. In order to study the effect of volume to mass ratio (*v/m* ratio), 20 ml of Pb^{II} stock solution (50 mg L⁻¹) was pipetted out into each of the reagent bottles

and pH of the solutions was adjusted to 5. Varying amounts of bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs such as 0.05 g, 0.067 g, 0.1 g and 0.2 g were added to each of these reagent bottles to get the v/m ratio of 400, 300, 200 and 100 folds, respectively. In order to study the effect of contact time, 20 ml of Pb^{II} stock solution (50 mg L^{-1}) was pipetted out into each of the reagent bottles and pH of the solutions was adjusted to 5. A 0.067g bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs was added to each of these reagent bottles to get the v/m ratio of 300 fold. Then the bottles were shaken for 30 min, 1 h, 4 h, and 24 h at 50 rpm. In order to study the effect of initial load, 500, 1000, 2000, 2500 and 3000 mg L^{-1} of Pb^{II} stock solutions were prepared. Twenty ml each of these solutions was pipetted out into the reagent bottles and pH of the solutions was adjusted to 5. A 0.025 g bimetallic Ni/Fe NPs was added to each of these reagent bottles in order to get a high v/m ratio of 800 as well as to avoid complete removal of Pb^{II} from the solution. Also, then the bottles were shaken for 24 h at 50 rpm. Similar to adsorption study using Ni/Fe NPs the effects of pH (pH 1–5), v/m ratio (100 to 400 folds), contact time (30 min to 24 h), and initial concentrations (500 to 4000 mg L^{-1}) were carried using nZVI. Finally the concentrations of Pb^{II} in the filtrate were estimated by flame AAS.

Calculation of metal uptake : The quality of sorption is judged by the metal uptake (sorption capacity), q (mg g^{-1}). Amount of Pb^{II} bound by the sorbent (e.g. nZVI or Ni/Fe NPs) was calculated based on the mass balance for the sorbent in the system. The ' q ' was determined by the equation : $q = V(C_i - C_f)/S$, where q = metal ion uptake capacity (mg g^{-1}), C_i = initial concentration of metal in solution before the sorption analysis (mg L^{-1}), C_f = final concentration of metal in solution after the sorption analysis (mg L^{-1}), S = dry weight of sorbent (mg) and V = solution volume (L). The assumption was that the difference between the initial metal ion concentration and final equilibrium metal ion concentration was bound to the sorbent.

Conclusions :

In the present study both Ni/Fe bimetallic NPs and nZVI show maximum removal of Pb^{II} at pH 5. In both the cases the removal efficiency is increased with increase in pH and this may be due to protonation or deprotonation of the hydroxyl species on the surface of NPs, but corrosion of nZVI in lower pH reduces its efficiency to 71.3%

compared to 98.1% by Ni/Fe NPs. Also, Ni-shell of bimetallic Ni/Fe core-shell NPs accelerates catalytic reduction of Pb^{II} ions which results greater removal efficiency than nZVI. Although identical equilibrium time and decreased removal efficiency with more initial load are observed, the effect of initial load is prominent on nZVI compared to Ni/Fe nanoparticle ($2275 \text{ mg Pb}^{II}/\text{g nZVI}$ vs $2311 \text{ mg Pb}^{II}/\text{g Ni/Fe}$). Also, results on adsorption isotherms suggest that adsorption process on Ni/Fe NPs is heterogeneous whereas that on nZVI is preferably homogeneous.

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Mandal *et al.* : Comparative studies of Pb^{II} remediation by zero-valent iron and bimetallic *etc.*

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